

Presentation checklist

- 7 statements of the persona are transformed into design ideas
- The statements are drawn and labeled on the mock-up
- 4 of the design ideas support sustainability and are labeled accordingly in the mock-up
- The presentation template is filled out
- The mock-up is ready for presentation
- The presentation content is divided between the group members